

PATTERNS OF STRUCTURAL AND FUNCTIONAL CHANGES IN PERIODONTAL TISSUES IN PATIENTS WITH BRUXISM

Marupov Shekhroz Shukhrat ugli¹

Mansurova Sabina Shavkat kizi²

¹⁻²Samarkand State Medical University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6590445>

Introduction. Treatment of periodontal diseases is currently one of the most pressing problems of dentistry. There are several theories of the origin of this pathology. According to many researchers, the cause of periodontitis, which is one of the first places, is bruxism [8, 11]. There are different opinions about the influence of bruxism on the development of traumatic occlusion. Thus, some researchers [3, 7, 11] believe that periodontal tissue damage may be the result of occlusive forces exceeding the reparative-adaptive capabilities of the clinical attachment apparatus. However, the diagnosis of occlusive trauma is made in cases when clinical signs appear in the form of pathological tooth mobility, changes in the position of the tooth in the dentition, tooth pain, discomfort during chewing or percussion and radiological changes: expansion of the periodontal gap, destruction of the compact bone plate, transparency in the area of bifurcation and the tip of the root of the vital tooth or the presence of root resorption. Occlusal trauma caused by excessive chewing loads on a healthy periodontal is called primary occlusal. Primary traumatic occlusion is a reversible process. When the traumatic area heals, an enlarged periodontal gap remains. It should be noted that traumatic occlusion does not cause apical migration of epithelial attachment or the development of pathological dentoalveolar pockets. In primary traumatic syndrome, periodontal dystrophy is determined only in the zone of functional overload, and in systemic diseases it is systemic in nature [1].

The purpose of the study. To study the patterns of structural and functional changes in periodontal tissues in patients with bruxism.

Materials and methods of research. To study the masticatory pressure developed at the time of "night gnashing", we examined 74 people (from 14 to 60 years old) suffering from bruxism, of whom 14 subjects were diagnosed with the latent stage, 17 patients had mild severity of the disease, 27 – moderate severity of bruxism and 16 – severe. The clinical comparison group consisted of 15 practically healthy people aged 20 to 25 years who do not have clinical signs of periodontal diseases and bruxism. To measure the effort developed by the masticatory muscles, we used the method proposed by T.A. Gaidarova (2003).

The sensor consists of a cap and a crown made according to a specific tooth so that the cap follows the shape of the tooth surface, and the crown follows the shape of the cap. Measuring balls in the amount of 3-15 pieces are located between the crowns in the most flat part. The number of balls is determined by their diameter, the plasticity of the material from which they are made, and the maximum expected compression force. The free space between the crowns is filled with a silicone composition that fixes the beads and holds the crowns together. The measuring balls were made of food grade solder with a diameter of 1 mm. Balls of this diameter have a greater curvature than the crowns compressing them at the points of contact. Therefore, it can be assumed that the balls are deformed, squeezed by flat surfaces. Round flat prints remain on the surface of the balls as a result of plastic deformation. According to the research results, the use of weak (small) orthodontic forces, up to 20 g / cm, has a stimulating effect on the bone formation process and helps to reduce the degree of pathological mobility. The analysis of radiographs also allowed the researchers to conclude that treatment with the use of small forces does not aggravate dystrophic processes. Since the load during the attacks of "night gnashing" is intermittent, the rest pauses allow the processes of tissue growth to prevail over the processes of resorption. The data of gnathodynamometric studies have shown that with an average degree of severity of bruxism, the pressure force per unit area of compact bone increases and amounts to 27.0 ± 1.9 g/cm. The impact of this magnitude is characterized as an average "orthodontic" force exceeding capillary pressure. It has been established that the use of such force causes anemia, stagnation of blood, pain.

Results. The results of the gnathodynamometric study showed that with a severe degree of the disease, the impact force at the time of the "night gnashing" attack in this category of patients increases to 47.0 ± 1.9 g / cm² and is characterized as a large "orthodontic", which leads to the destruction of the cortical bone, pathological mobility and inflammation of the marginal periodontal.

Conclusion. Thus, the results of a gnathodynamometric study of patients with bruxism showed that the magnitude of the load on the cortical layer of the alveolar well at the time of attacks of "night gnashing" in mild and severe cases of the disease differs slightly and is characterized as intermittent small and medium "orthodontic" force, which, with a decrease in the area of the cortical layer of the alveolar well, outgrows the large discharge, which leads to inflammatory and destructive process in periodontal tissues.

Literature

1. Belousov N.N., Bulanov V.I. Problems of examination and diagnosis in periodontal diseases // Dentistry. - 2004. – No. 2. – pp. 19-20.
2. Velichko L.S., Poloneychik N.M., Krushevsky A.E. Determination of the residual periodontal capacity taking into account the angle of inclination of the teeth // Dentistry. – 1985. – No. 4. – pp. 20-21.
3. Gavrilov E.I., Pantelev V.D. Clinical forms of parafunctions of masticatory muscles // Dentistry. – 1987. – No. 4. – pp. 40-43.
4. Gavrilov E.I., Pantelev V.D. Features of orthopedic care for patients with parafunctions of masticatory muscles // Dentistry. - 1990. – No. 5 – pp. 80-81.
5. Gaidarova T.A. Mechanisms of formation and pathogenetic principles of treatment of bruxism: Dis. ... doctor of medical sciences. – Irkutsk, 2003. – p. 213.
6. Gaidarova T.A. Method and device for measuring the maximum compression force of teeth / Patent for invention No. 2231995 of 10.07.2004.
7. Gross M.D., Matthew J.D. Normalization of occlusion / Translated from English – M.: Medicine, 1986. – 287 p.
8. Zhulev E.N. Etiology, clinic and treatment of bruxism // Dentistry. – 1976. – No. 4. – pp. 95-98.

